

ISic0163

I.Sicily inscription 0163

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis · Manibus ·

2. Cornelia · Scepsis ·

3. vix(it) · an(nis) · □ · XXXVIII ·

4. Auctus · coniugi ·

5. piissim(ae) · fec(it)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

There is no immediately clear answer as to what the sign "□", a reverse C, symbolises here; cf. ISicily0146, CIL 6.15139 (Rome) for analogous use, as pointed out by Bivona (1994). Understanding □ as deriving from 'circiter' is one attractive interpretation.

Translation (en)

To the Shades of the Underworld. Cornelia Scepsis; she lived [almost?] 38 years. Auctus erected this for his most dutiful wife.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175699

EDR 077917

EDCS 8900395

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0517

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 84

Bivona, L 1975-1976. Nuove iscrizioni di Termini Imerese (Palermo). *Atti della Accademia di Scienze, Lettere e Arti di Palermo*. Ser.4, vol.35: 531-558. At 542 no.5 tav.3

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